

Teaching Microchemistry in Industry Versus Teaching in a University

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In an industrial company, the beginner must be able to produce results in as short a time as possible so he or she is taught one determination at a time, whereas in a university, the student receives a full course.

TWO methods of teaching microchemistry are in general use. Industrial companies are interested in having the new employee to be able to produce results in as short a time as possible and concentrate on having he or she becoming efficient in one determination. Some companies employ persons having college or university degrees while others use persons who have no degree but who have had elementary courses in chemistry. In the author's laboratory at Hoffmann-La Roche, before he retired, he had all college or university graduates who have had courses in analytical chemistry (macro), organic chemistry and in some cases physical chemistry.

After being taught the use of the microchemical balance, the individual was allowed to determine metals by the ashing technique, which he continued to do for several days to gain more weighing experience.

The next step was the teaching of the determination of nitrogen by the Dumas method. After repeating this a number of times during the next few weeks, the beginner was experienced enough to be allowed to "graduate" from running known test compounds to do so on research samples, and was then kept doing this determination for several months.

Next followed, using the same procedure, the determinations of carbon-hydrogen by the classical method, halogens, sulfur, phosphorus, nitrogen by the Kjeldahl method, arsenic, automatic carbon-hydrogen-nitrogen, alkoxy, molecular weight, etc., all of the determinations described in the author's text book¹. Obviously, the more experienced the individual became, the less time and number of test compounds were needed when a new determination was done. Depending upon the person, one to two years was required before analysts were efficient in all types of determinations. In this way there could be rotation of the work, which was necessary to prevent monotony.

At the University, the author gives a one semester course in which the students spend six hours per week for fourteen weeks in the laboratory. Although there have been as many as twenty-six students taking the course at one time, the course is operated on a "by arrangement" schedule basis so that not more than four students are in the

laboratory at any one time. This allows for much individual attention so that the students receive the extra benefit. The object of the course is to teach students how to handle small amounts of material with accuracy and precision, rather than to create microchemists. The students must have passed courses in analytical chemistry (macro) and organic chemistry. A few of the students are third year undergraduates and a few are graduate students who are candidates for the master or doctor degree. The majority are in their last semester before receiving the bachelor degree.

Each student is required to determine (in duplicate) halogens by the Carius method¹ and the oxygen flask mercurimetric method², nitrogen by both the Dumas¹ and Kjeldahl¹ methods, carbon-hydrogen by the classical method¹, carbon-hydrogen-nitrogen by automatically, arsenic¹, sulfur¹, phosphorus gravimetrically¹ and titrimetrically³, alkoxy¹, molecular weight by the two isothermal distillation methods¹, boiling points, melting points¹ and specific gravity¹. The results obtained are unusually good. Some students obtain acceptable results¹ in as many as twenty-five out of twenty-six or twenty-seven determinations.

After having taken the regular course, some students do research, as for example the work done on the alkoxy determination⁴, in which it was found that by using the regular apparatus and procedure¹, the sample size could be reduced to as low as less than 100 μg and acceptable results¹ obtained consistently.

After teaching the course for the past thirteen years, during which approximately two hundred students took the course only four have positions as microchemists. Many of the others repeatedly advise that, although they are not doing actual micro work, their micro training has been of extreme value to them in their fields.

References

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